

ON THE EFFECT OF MQL PARAMETERS ON MACHINING QUALITY OF CFRP

Y. Iskandar¹, A. Damir², M.H. Attia^{1,2*}, P. Hendrick³

¹Mechanical Engineering Department, McGill University, Montreal, Canada,

²Aerospace Manufacturing, National Research Council Canada (NRC), Montreal, Canada

³Université Libre de Bruxelles, Bruxelles, Belgium

* Corresponding author (helmi.attia@nrc.ca / helmi.attia@mcgill.ca)

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1 General Introduction

New manufacturing paradigms involve more dependence on green manufacturing techniques. Minimum Quantity Lubrication (MQL) of machining processes has gained significant interest by replacing the conventional flood cooling in many applications involving various materials and cutting conditions [1,2]. The use of this technique results in considerable reductions in the quantity of lubricant used, reducing manufacturing costs, as well as the impact of the process on the environment. Review of previous work on machining with MQL showed promising results. The technology appears to have a niche of applications, where it would prove beneficial in terms of quality and savings, in addition to the environmental benefits [3].

Application of MQL in machining requires special considerations to ensure that the cutting fluid adequately covers the cutting zone area, mainly, the tool–chip and the tool–workpiece interfaces. It is mostly required that the droplet size in the spray be relatively small for better penetration into the cutting surface [4]. However, small droplets < 4 µm in diameter are considered as mist, which are airborne fluid particles and can cause health issues if inhaled by the machine operators, depending on the type of oil used and its concentration [5].

In the machining process, the particle size and velocity characteristics of the MQL spray strongly influence the lubrication and cooling capacity of the jet. Heat generation due to friction at the tool–chip interface can increase tool wear and alters the quality of the machined surface. In the case of metal cutting, this affects the plastic deformation process in the primary and secondary shear zones [6]. In

addition, it creates residual stresses in the machined surface and results in thermal deformation of the cutting tool [7]. A good understanding of the lubrication and cooling effects at the cutting zone will lead to efficient and economic machining [6].

Several studies evaluated the effect of the application of MQL on the machining performance, as compared to dry cutting and machining with flood coolants. In drilling of magnesium alloy [8], carbon steel [9] and aluminum-silicon alloy [10], the application of MQL showed lower cutting forces and temperature and better surface quality, when compared to dry and flood coolant. Additionally, lower tool wear was associated with MQL in the drilling of hardened steel [11] and aluminum silicon alloy [10]. In milling of steel [12-14], titanium alloy [15] and aluminum 6161 [16, 17], MQL showed also lower tool wear lower cutting forces, and better surface quality. Similarly, MQL application in turning showed lower cutting temperatures and tool wear when machining steel [18-20], and Inconel 718 [21], as compared to dry and flood coolant. Even in grinding of titanium alloys [22] and hardened steel [23], MQL showed lower cutting forces and surface roughness.

However, there is limited knowledge of the flow regimes through which MQL functions. The presence of different methods of atomization has a great impact on the nature of the aerosols generated, and hence, its cooling and lubrication capabilities. Additionally, the machining of difficult-to-cut materials; e.g., Inconel and Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastics using MQL did not have its fair share of investigation. Therefore, the main objective of this work is to study the effect of MQL parameters, namely, the air flow rate (V_a) and oil flow rate (V_o),

on the quality of the machined surface in routing of Carbon-Fiber Reinforced Plastics (CFRP) laminates. The machining quality was evaluated in terms of the surface roughness and the geometrical accuracy of the machined surface. Comparison of MQL to dry and flood cooling is also presented.

2 Experimental Work

Routing experiments were performed to study the effect of MQL parameters and different cooling techniques on the machining quality of CFRP laminates. The tests were designed so that all machining parameters would be fixed with only the tribological conditions changing. Three MQL conditions were considered along with flood cooling, pressurized air, and dry machining. Tables

Table 1 shows the test matrix of the cooling conditions used in these experiments. The routing experiments were performed on a 5-axis DMU 100P duo BLOCK® CNC Machining Center, at the Aerospace Manufacturing Technology Center (AMTC) of the National Research Council Canada (NRC). The setup was designed to ensure the collection of the CFRP dust generated without intervention of the application of MQL and the collection of the data, as shown in Figure 1. The test samples were mounted vertically and slotting operations were performed. The cutting conditions were fixed at a cutting speed of 15,000 rpm and a feed of 1,500 mm/min, resulting in a nominal chip load of 0.025 mm/tooth. Mecagreen 550 was used to make a 5% concentration emulsion for the MQL tests.

Dimensional and geometrical features of the machined slots, as well as, the tool wear were evaluated, for each cutting condition, after 90 mm cutting length, for a total length of 450 mm. This allows assessing the progressive evolution of the quality of the machined surface, in relation to the progressive flank wear.

Routing slots of 90 mm in length and 6.35 mm wide were machined according to the layout shown in Figure 2. A pilot hole was first drilled at each cutting location to permit tool to penetrate the full axial depth of cut (i.e. the workpiece thickness), before the routing process. All cuts were performed using helical 4-flute 1/4" uncoated tungsten-carbide

endmills (SGS-30131). The tool selection criterion was to combine the elevated hardness of tungsten-carbide with its moderate cost (compared to coated carbide tools). It should be noted that uncoated carbide tools are commonly used in industrial applications.

3 Results and discussions

3.1 Tool wear

Figure 3 shows the progressive flank wear measurements for the tested cooling conditions at different cutting length. The superior effect of MQL in controlling tool wear can be seen, as compared to other cooling techniques. All three MQL conditions resulted in lower tool wear than those obtained with pressurized air, dry and flood cooling. The reduction in the tool wear when using MQL is up to 22% to 30%, compared to air, dry and flood cooling. This can be attributed to the better jet penetration and atomization, and hence, better cooling and lubrication when the MQL parameters are properly selected. Figure 4 shows the flank wear for both cases of pressurized air and MQL with 10 ml/hr oil flow rate (V_o) and 30 l/min air flow rate (V_a) after 450 mm cutting length.

Among the MQL conditions, lower tool wear was observed for the case of minimum oil flow rate ($V_o = 10$ ml/min) and maximum air flow rate ($V_a = 31$ l/min). Under these conditions, the reduction in the flank wear reaches 17% as compared to other MQL combinations. This can be attributed to the jet characteristics associated with the Max V_a /Min V_o MQL combination; lower droplet size, higher droplet velocity and lower vorticity which promote the droplet penetration, evaporation and hence, the heat transfer capacity of the jet [24].

The flank wear from MQL cuts with Max V_o /Min V_a are higher than those of the Max V_o /Max V_a MQC condition, except in the last two segments. The abrupt increase in the tool wear for the Max V_o /Max V_a condition at the 4th cut segment (8 μ m) was a breakage that was not consistent with the process, and is most likely a damage that took place during tool entry and retraction.

It is interesting to note that flood cooling and dry machining modes resulted in higher tool wear than MQL. The abundance of water and moisture in flood

cooling has adverse effects on the matrix integrity. This is less likely under MQL since the dispensed lubricant amounts are significantly lower, and the incumbent pressurized air on the workpiece facilitates the rapid evaporation of the liquid. Additionally, the presence of lubricant in MQL gave better tool performance over dry cutting. This promotes the application of MQL in machining of composites over dry machining, which is currently the most industrially employed method with CFRPs.

3.2 Dimensional and geometrical accuracy

The cut CFRP slots were analyzed for geometric accuracy using a Mitutoyo MACH806 coordinate measuring machine. The width of cut, straightness, and parallelism errors were measured at two depths 4.35 mm apart for each cut, and on both sides of the slot (top and bottom), to cover the geometrical features of the machined surface. Figure 5 shows an example of the measured geometrical features for MQL condition of Min. $V_o=10$ ml/min and Max. $V_a=31$ l/min. A tolerance of ± 25 μm over the width of cut was selected, while a straightness and parallelism values below 100 μm are considered acceptable.

Comparing the different modes of cooling/lubrication, it was observed that with the exception of the (Min V_o /Max V_a), all initial segments had higher than the nominal width of 6.35 mm as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** This was clear in the initial cut segments. However, the progressive tool wear with the increase in the cutting length (≥ 360 mm) reduced the width of cut below the lower tolerance limit, especially in the case of dry and MQL machining.

For the initial cuts in case of dry mode, pressurized air mode, flood coolant and MQL lubrication with high oil flow rate V_o (24 ml/min) and low air flow rate V_a (20 l/min), the resulted width of cut was out of tolerance with a higher than nominal value. However, for the remaining cuts, most of the cooling conditions gave a width of cut within the acceptable tolerance as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** It is evident that machining with MQL with Min V_o /Max V_a (10 ml/hr and 30 l/min) resulted in the most stable width of cut throughout the cutting distance as compared to other MQL combination, as well as, dry cutting, air and flood

coolant. This is demonstrated by the least variation of the width of cut ($\leq 9\mu\text{m}$) with respect to the nominal value as shown in Figure 7. This observation is in agreement with the corresponding low tool wear associated with Min V_o /Max V_a that led to a stable width of cut. The difference in the results between the minimum V_o / maximum V_a combination, and combinations with higher V_o or flood cooling, is indicative of the better lubrication and cooling capacity of minimal quantities, if the atomization quality of the jet is appropriate.

The tribological conditions did not seem to have any remarkable effect on the straightness and parallelism errors over the distance of 450 mm. The resulted straightness and parallelism errors were within the acceptable tolerance for the tested cooling conditions (≤ 100 μm) as shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9.

The geometrical errors showed a dependence on the workpiece fiber orientation, despite near-isotropic properties of the material. Cuts under the same tribological conditions, but performed on different plates, showed sharp jumps in these errors depending on the fiber orientation. Therefore, the weave orientation of the workpiece had the predominant effect on the straightness and parallelism errors, but did not have any effect on the width of cut.

4 Conclusions

The effect of different cooling methods on the machining quality of CFRP was investigated. The performance of different combinations of MQL as compared to dry, pressurized air and flood coolant was evaluated in milling of CFRP. The performance was evaluated in terms of tool wear and the quality of the machined surface, with respect to dimensional and geometrical errors.

Better tool life was obtained when machining using MQL as compared to dry, air and flood cooling. This was shown by the 30% reduction in flank wear as compared to air and 22% as compared to dry and flood coolant. This favorable effect can be attributed to the better jet penetration and atomization for MQL when its parameters are properly selected. These attributes lead to better cooling and lubrication capacity and, hence, the improvement of the tool life. Among MQL combinations, lower tool

wear was found for the case of maximum air flow rate and minimum oil flow rate. This is mainly due to the smaller droplet size, higher droplet velocity and lower vorticity associated with the Min Vo/Max Va MQL combination.

Similar trends were observed regarding the dimensional accuracy with the (Min Vo/Max Va) MQL combination as compared to dry, air, flood and other MQL combinations. This condition showed the best dimensional stability, with the least variation of the width of cut. The geometrical features showed dependence on the workpiece fiber orientation rather than on the tribological conditions.

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Tables

Table 1 – Tested cooling conditions

Condition	Coolant	Va (l/min)	Vo (ml/min)
1	Air	31	N/A
2	Flood	N/A	N/A
3	Dry	N/A	N/A
4	MQL	31	24
5	MQL	20	24
6	MQL	31	10

Figures

Figure 1 - Experimental setup for routing of CFRP

Figure 2 - Workpiece layout

Figure 3 - Flank wear progression for different cooling conditions

Figure 4 - Flank wear after 450 mm of cutting. (a) Max Vo/Min Va; (b) Pressurized Air

Figure 5 - Dimensional and Geometric accuracy progression for MQL condition (Min $V_o = 10$ ml/hr, Max $V_a = 30$ l/min)

Figure 6 – Progression of width of cut for different cooling conditions

Figure 7- Progression of width of cut variation for different cooling conditions

Figure 8 – Parallelism error progression for different cooling conditions

Figure 9 – Straightness error progression for different cooling conditions